

IFAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

MILESTONE REPORT

WP2 Task Leaders' Kick-off Meeting

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ABSTRACT

A kick-off meeting of the WP2 Task Leaders was held on 2 June 2021. Each Task Leader informed the team of the scope of her/his task and the plans for task activities, aiming towards timely achievement of the Milestones and Deliverables.

IFAST Consortium, 2021

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The WP2 Task Leaders kick-off meeting was held on 2 June 2021 to review scope and plans for the WP2 task activities, aiming towards timely achievement of the Milestones and Deliverables.

1. Introduction

A kick-off meeting of the WP2 Task Leaders was held on 2 June 2021. Each Task Leader informed the team of the scope of her/his task and the plans for task activities, leading towards timely achievement of the Milestones and Deliverables.

2. Attendees, via zoom.

WP manager, and Task 2.1: P.N. Burrows

Task 2.2: D. Antonio, A. Le Gall

Task 2.3: N. Delerue in absentia represented by P.N. Burrows

Task 2.4: T. Ekelof

WP2 Coordinator and Task Leader 2.1	P. N. Burrows
Task Leader 2.2	D. Antonio, A. Le Gall
Task Leader 2.3	N. Delerue (represented by P.N. Burrows)
Task Leader 2.4	T. Ekelof

3. Agenda

- Task 2.1 Management
- Task 2.2 Communications and Outreach
- Task 2.3 Challenge-based innovation
- Task 2.4 Industrial training with knowledge transfer

4. Conclusions

All tasks have launched successfully and commenced their activities.